

SPEAKING COMPETENCE IN AN ESP CONTEXT (A CASE STUDY OF ENGINEERING STUDENTS)

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Abstract

Speaking, apart from having the status of being the primary means of communication in general, it is one of the main mediums of communication in a foreign language class and at the same time, one of the key components of a foreign language syllabus. For most students, it is regarded as a skill that does not require much prior preparation, however, when taking tests, the speaking section is the one that causes the most anxiety. Learning a language does not necessarily mean speaking it. Learners need to be taught the right techniques and apply the useful strategies to be used while speaking and this is done by bearing in mind the aim one wants to achieve (narrate, summarize, give instructions, express viewpoints, justify opinions etc.) and the assessment criteria and the positive outcome of speaking. A considerable number of activities in textbooks are oriented towards speaking. To ESP students, in our case, engineering students, part of the speaking preparation, the one closely related to the lexicon, is covered with the introduction of the field-related terminology. Still, there are other aspects that need to be considered and developed by the students. Most of the lesson time is spent on talking, held either between the teacher and the student or among students. In the ESP textbooks used in our University, a considerable number of the activities are oriented towards oral communication with the aim of equipping future professionals with the right speaking skills for effective interaction with other coworkers. A high-frequency practice during the lesson is one appropriate approach, the positive results of which are obvious the moment 'the message' is fully conveyed and there is linguistic interaction.

Keywords: speaking, teaching, ESP, techniques, assessment.

Objective

This paper aims to pinpoint the Speaking activities in ESP classes as the ones that require a particular approach, specific techniques and lots of practice for the students to fully have a good command of it. Speaking is a dominant activity during a foreign language class and one of the four skills learners will have to be evaluated either for the final evaluation of the syllabus or for international exams of English. In this study, we will give an overview of the current situation of Speaking Skills in an ESP context and also reach conclusions on some strategies we believe might be useful to our learners to develop good speaking skills and build confidence in this life-long needed skill.

Methodology

For the conduct of this study, the approach used is the observational one, which is done in our English classes with the engineering students at the Polytechnic University of Tirana. The observation is also based on our experience as Speaking Examiners of English. Discussions are held with students, mini-surveys are done as well as analysis of the textbooks in order for us to have a full and clear picture of the obstacles they face.

Introduction

Speaking skills are vital to a good understanding of a foreign language and communication among people. It is a skill developed during a person's study cycle and a skill useful in one's career throughout the entire life. According to Srinivas Rao, P. (2019), Brown and

Yule (1983) described speaking as the skill students will be judged upon most in real-life situations. He highlights the importance of speaking by stating that 'the one who has good talent in speaking can conquer the entire world.'

Shehu I. (2024) estimates presentation skills, a speaking activity, as one key competence and a huge asset the learner should possess and be well-rounded during one's studies.

Burns, A. (2019) concludes that the main aim of speaking tasks is to help students develop the fluency of natives, where meaning is communicated with few hesitations.

Thornbury, S (2005) specifically states that learning a language does not necessarily mean speaking that language. This fully supports our idea of first making students aware of the importance of acquiring such skills.

From an overview of the units in some of the Engineering textbooks used at our University, almost every unit starts with a warm-up activity, which is a discussion of a couple of questions through which learners start activating language and through which their interest is sparked. It constitutes 33% of the activities per unit, with another exercise in which students are asked to act out and simulate real-life and career-specific situations. Employing these guided speaking exercises, they are asked to practice useful language/phrases and sample language taught earlier in the

unit, practice the branch-related terminology and at the same time, recall other general speaking conventions and grammar rules which are not peculiar to language for specific purposes only, but general language too. It is inevitable to correct other speaking components such as pronunciation, stress, intonation and the register. This approach fully aligns with the communicative output (Ramadhani, P:2017) used in teaching Speaking skills.

Analysis

Regarding lexicon, unlike other EFL learners who struggle with limited vocabulary, our ESP students do not struggle much due to the high exposure to terminology in the textbooks used, specifically tailored for engineers. By applying the content-oriented method, the teacher encourages the learner to put into practice pre-taught vocabulary.

Via grammar, the learner is able to put words together and accurately use them. Grammar together with vocabulary is the first criterion assessed in a speaking activity and in the case of ESP students, basic grammar knowledge is required and taken for granted.

Pronunciation, the ability of the user to clearly produce sounds, is one of the Speaking Criteria in which learners get the highest points. Researchers of the Albanian language attribute this gifted skill of our learners to the relatively great number of phones (36 phonemes – 29 consonants and 7 vowels) in Albanian language, similarity in phonetic systems and probably the geographical position believed to influence linguistic sounds.

Speaking is regarded as the most active and spontaneous skill and it involves interaction. The reflection of this is seen in dialogues and discussions held in class, simulating real-life interaction. In the case of role-play, they push learners into creatively reacting to a situation, thus developing fluency, which is a key feature of natives. Interaction is one fundamental component of Speaking and requires learners to actively participate in listening and speaking. Pair work or group work are very useful activities that lead to interaction.

Elaborating on the ability to respond and be able to talk about any subject, is another skill strongly practised by the teachers, who time after time require learners to come up with an idea and a response, even when they have the least knowledge on the topic.

We believe that the cultural element in speaking is to a certain degree missing in the engineering textbooks, being of a technical character. However, culture can never be separated from language. As Sozen, P.H. (2016) puts it, it is inescapable to see culture, language and communication as a whole. Learning and practicing one language is equivalent to learning the culture of the place it is spoken. It is to be said that such elements are used to a large extent in EFL classes. Nevertheless, introduction to cultural elements in ESP class is done by the lecturer, and indirectly by the set phrases taught and used in conversations which in ESP might be informal or formal. Understanding cultural differences is essential in achieving effective communication and it

greatly impacts how a message is received and this applies in the ESP context as well.

Speaking is a spontaneous process and this characteristic is directly attributed to the fear of the learner to express oneself in a foreign language. As the saying goes, practice makes perfect, and this fully aligns with the case of teaching speaking in an ESL/EFL context. One way to best fight anxiety and build confidence in a foreign language learner is to give corrective, formative and encouraging feedback that motivates the student.

Recommendations

It is up to the lecturer to select from the various techniques to apply in teaching speaking. Among the most effective and commonly used techniques in teaching Speaking skills is to encourage learners to actively ask and answer questions, introduce and share ideas, engage in role-playing activities, give presentations, interpret images, tell stories, etc. Regardless of the strategies, speaking skills of ESP students have to be developed as they constitute the most frequent activity that learners will always be assessed and that will always play a part in a person's success in life. During the speaking process, learners may guess, interact with the interlocutor in English even by paraphrasing (not switching to Albanian), and dare to express ideas regardless of the fear of making mistakes.

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